

Need of Information and Information Seeking Behavior of Public Library in Yobe State: A Case Study of Geidam Local Govt

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Abstract:- As we are in the era of information need, it is among of the tasks of librarians to know what types of information their clientele requires in order to satisfy their information thirst, this study will try to investigate those information need and the ways to follows for satisfying them, with the help of these objectives:

- To identify the information need of Geidam public library users
- To find out their information seeking behavior
- To find out the challenges faced by them in information seeking
- To suggest possible solutions to those problems

Survey method was adopted for this research, frequency and percentage was used in the analysis.

Keywords:- *Information Need, Information Seeking Behavior, Public Library.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

We are living in the information age. This is to indicate the importance of information for survival and progress in now a day. Any activity that we do today requires input of information. This may be of individuals, institution or even nations. Decision making cannot be ascertain without information, teaching and learning to add to our knowledge base. It implies that it is required by the head of a staff, a manager, a teacher, a scholar, a student etc.

Information- seeking behavior varies among user groups. Geidam public library staff must understand the information needs of all the clients in order to address those needs. This study explores the information seeking behavior of Geidam public library users. This task has become more important with information seeking behavior. To access the information pin pointedly, exhaustively and expeditiously organized by the study library services have become essential this is because Information is a great phenomenon which has led to man's progress as I have said earlier. It is a basic resource for any kind of activity. The scientists, technologists, students, teachers, researchers, professionals require pinpointed, exhaustive information before taking a

decision. According to Wilson, (1981) a general model of information seeking behavior needs to include at least the following three elements:

- An information need and its drivers, i.e., the factors that gives rise to an individual's perception of need;
- The factor that affect the individual's response to the perception of need; and
- The processes or action involved in that response.

Information seeking behavior in information can be seeing as that which is concerned with determining user's information needs, searching behavior and subsequent use of information in other words is a disciplines concerned with understanding how people seek information and make use of it couple with the channel to follow as ascertain by Tubachi, Padmavati (2018).

➤ *Problem Statement*

Information has become integral part of every one lives in now a day for some purpose and it is the responsibility of any library to satisfy those needs of their clients, this research will highlight those information needs and seeking behavior of Geidam public library users in order to address them.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

The following objectives will guide me toward conducting this research:

- To identify the information need of Geidam public library users
- To find out their information seeking behavior
- To find out the challenges faced by them
- To suggest possible solutions to those problems

II. RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Introduction*

Literature review serve as a linkage between past and present this is to say literature review helps researchers in understanding the methods adopted in previous research, to the gap available in the area and the findings derived from the researches.

Information seeking behavior is a broad term and refers to those excise that an individual takes to expressive, seek, evaluate, select and finally use the required information for meeting his/her information needs **S Majid & Kassim (2000)**.

This connote with words of **Liao, Finn, & Lu, (2007)** where they explored the process involved in information seeking behavior of international graduate students versus American graduate students and the information seeking process was divided into three stages namely initiating, searching and location stage.

Jeong, (2004)in his article on Korean graduate student's for everyday information seeking behavior in the United State. The results indicate that Korean students rarely read local or national newspaper and few watched television, lack of good English skills prevent them from interacting with the American society, they gather information through ethnic community in setting things such as Korean church. Language barrier discourage them from taking interest in current events and hindered students from travelling outside their university's city and learning about the area.

Abdoulay k., (2002) conducted research on information seeking behavior of international African students at International Islamic University Malaysia he found most of the respondents are fully aware of the services provided by the university library. Respondent were also found to be relying heavily on library books such as textbooks, periodical journal, and the internet on their both course work and research work.

In her research **Safahieh,(2007)**information need and information seeking behavior of international student in Malaysia. The study used questionnaire-based surveyed method on sample of 204 randomly selected international students from three major public universities in Malaysia namely University of Malaya, University of Putra Malaysia and National University Malaysia. Based on the analysis of the respondents who came from 32 different countries, more than 70% perceived themselves as being computer and internet literate and having a good level of English language proficiency. Their main information needs were related to their program of the study. The internet and library is their main source of information. In attempting to meet their information need they face some barriers, most of the barriers are language barrier, lack of awareness in arrangement of library materials and also reluctant to approach reference station and professional librarians. Despite the barrier more than half (52%) of the respondents had not received any formal instruction from the library and this is a great set back to the library.

Song, (2004) focuses his study on international business student population at University of Illinois by their comparing information seeking behavior to that local business student. The questionnaire based survey was used to investigate if local and business international student had different perception and behavior in assessing the

effectiveness of instruction session, and using the library and its services. Based on the results found from the 84 respondents, Song found that the library instruction session greatly helped international business students in learning the library databases and other services. International business students realized that the library database introduced during instruction session could provide valuable information for their specific projects, they became motivated to use library databases and seek assistance from the library more often than before. This show library instruction had great impact on international business students' seeking behavior than the local business student. Furthermore, the results show local business student visit library rear than international business student do but they use electronic resources from remote location than the international business student. The local business student takes the library as primary place of research while the international business student perceived it as a place of study. The research was concluded that international business student perceptions of library services are based on previous experienced with library services in their home countries. Their perceptions of library services are mainly shaped by unique formal system and requirement in their home countries. However, instruction plays a crucial role in changing international students' previous experiences and perceptions. As a result, the library is considered as a simply as a place to study but also as a provider of relevant information to enhance their learning.

Singh, Kumar, & Khanchandani, (2015) investigate the information need and information seeking behavior of foreign student in University of Delhi. A survey method was used for undertaking the study. The data were collected using a structured questionnaire, self-administered to 120 foreign students (60 male & 60 female) with 88 (47 male & 41 female) returns. The research is limited to postgraduate, MPhil and PhD foreign student of university of Delhi. The researcher found that postgraduate student needs information regarding their program of study while research scholars need information for writing research article and for doing their research work. Internet is the source of their information. More than 80% of the respondent book and article are used in term of the method for information seeking behavior and few are asking librarian's help. It was also found the response of international student visit central library with more than 65% and visit the library many times in a semester with more 50%. It is also revealed more than 80% of the international student encountered with some problem in their meeting information need. 71% of the respondent reported that there are too few computer terminals in the library followed by 67% who found that the library had old materials and this could be the main reason behind poor use of libraries. Female student had more problems in using the library catalogue/ OPAC. As they had less knowledge of how to use the library and they are also unable to evaluate the obtained information.

Okoh & Ijiekhuamhen, (2007) investigate the information seeking behavior of undergraduate of federal university of petroleum in Nigeria. A structured questionnaire was used for data gathering in the university. The questionnaire data was analyzed using frequency, bar

chart and percentage for easy interpretation. The research found that more 60% of the respondent use Google or other search engine as their source of information. Most of the respondent obtained information because of academics and assignment with 78% and 68% respectively. The factors affecting information seeking behavior of the respondents were lack of computer skill; irregular electricity supply and lack of good search skill were found.

Fidzani, (2005) carried out a study on the information needs and information seeking behavior of graduate students at the University of Botswana. The study aimed to determine the student information requirements and awareness of library services available to them. A closed ended questionnaire uses to collect data from 144 students out of 233 part-time and full time graduate students registered. The findings of the study revealed there was heavy reliance on library book, textbook and journal as a source of information used for course work. Student relied on scanning shelves or browsing through journals rather than using the index and abstract databases to locate information. Only 40% seek help from the reference librarian. Most of the respondent lack awareness of how to use the library as well as the services available in the library. The researcher suggested marketing the library services to the users in order to promote utilizing the services.

ELLIS, COX, & HALL, (1993) investigated the information seeking patterns of social scientists, physicists and chemists using the ground theory approach with focus on describing activities rather than a process. Ellis identified five features of academic’s information seeking, including initial familiarization, chasing, source prioritization; maintaining awareness and locating. A later study by Ellis on academic researchers in other disciplines added more activities, including, verifying and ending.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study hasadopting survey method in order to retrieved the data that is through questionnaire, 200questionnaires was administered to the users of Geidam Public library, only 195 filled questionnaire was retrieved from the responded. We use SPSS for data analysis.

Table 1 Shows The Age Distribution

S No.	Age Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
1.	10-20	40	21%
2.	21-30	28	14%
3.	31-40	79	41%
4.	41 and above	48	24%
5.	Total	195	100%

➤ *Information Needs*

This subheading will give details of the information needs of the respondents on the types of information they need.

A. *Data Presentation and Analysis*

This chapter tries to portray the data collected through questionnaire, this chapter was categories into subheadings as follows:

➤ *Demographic Information*

The respondents are of two category based on gender that is male and their counterpart female the former are 115 which represent 59% of the respondent are male and later are 80 which represent 41% of the respondent as represented in the below pie chart

Chart 1 The Chart above Depict the Gender Distribution of the Respondent

The age group of the respondent 10 to 20 received 40 responses which 21%, 21-30 recieved 28 responses which represent 14% of the responseses, 31-40 scored the highest score of 79 responses which represent 41% and 41- and above got 48 responses which responses 24%.

The table 2 below shows the information need by the public Library users in Geidam. 26% of the respondents they need information to develop their career, 70 of the respondent are looking for information for a leisure which represent 36% of responses received where 15%, 13%, and 10% of the responses are in need of information news, seeking for job, and other information tha is not mentioned in the option respectively.

Table 2 Above Shows Information Need

S No.	Information Need	Frequency	Percentage
1.	To develop my career	50	26%
2.	For leisure	70	36%
3.	For news	30	15%
4.	For job	25	13%
5.	Other	20	10%
6.	Total	195	100

Table 3 Indicate the Reasons for Information Need

S No.	Reason for Information Need	Frequency	Percentage
1.	For writing article	50	26%
2.	For continue education	70	36%
3.	For current affairs	30	15%
4.	To be employed	25	13%
5.	Other	20	10%
6.	Total	195	100

Table 3 above depicts the reasons for information. Among the reason for information need are writing article where it received 50 responses, continue education is also part of the responses that received 70 responses, current affairs got 15% of the responses received, 13% of the responses goes to side they need information so that they will be employed and the last option others reasons that is not being mentioned in the option with 10%.

➤ Information Seeking Behaviour

From the table 4 shows the result of the library they prepared most. The result indicate more than half of the responses they prepare public library, followed by academic library, school library and private library while national with null response.

Table 4 Shows the Result of the Library you Prefer Most

S No.	Library you Prefer Most	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Academic library	49	25%
2.	Public library	100	51%
3.	Private library	1	0.5%
4.	National library	0	0%
5.	School library	45	23%
6.	Total	195	100

Table 5 Shows the Result of the Sources of Information Consulted Most

S No.	Source of Information Consulted Most	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Textbook	49	25%
2.	Journal Article	60	31%
3.	Newspaper	30	15%
4.	Other	56	29%
5.	Total	195	100

Sources of information they consulted most was depicted in the table 5 above. Textbook received 49 responses, article received 60, newspaper with 30 responses other sources that are not available in option provided received 56 responses.

Table 6 Indicate Frequency of Library Visitation

S No.	Frequency of Library Visitation in a Week	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Daily	29	14%
2.	Once in a week	70	36%
3.	A times	40	21%
4.	Two times in a week	25	13%
5.	Any other	31	16%
6.	Total	195	100

Table 6 shows the result of frequency of library visitation. Frequency of library visitation indicate how much you love reading, daily visit come out with 29 responses, where once in a week with the highest score of 70 responses, a times received 40 responses, two times in a week with the least score of 25 respond and other frequency received 31 responses.

Method of document retrieval are revealed in the table 7, where the result indicates more than half of the responses retrieved document through direct searching method, only 20 can retrieved document through catalogue, 44 response seek help from the librarians, 17 responses they recieved suggestion from their colleauge, and only 9 respond are using other method to retrieved document in the area of the study.

Table 7 Show Method of Document Retrieval in the Library

S No.	Method of Document Retrieval in Library	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Direct searching shelfe	105	54%
2.	Through catalogue	20	10%
3.	Seeking librarians help	44	23%
4.	Suggest by some one	17	9%
5.	Other	9	4%
6.	Total	195	100

Table 8 depict the result of do you have e-library. Yes with 51 responses that is 26% of the responses and in the other hand No with 144 responses which is 74% of the total respond received.

Table 8 Depicts the Presence of e-Library in the Library

S No.	Do you have e-Library	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Yes	51	25%
2.	No	144	74%
3.	Total	195	100

Table 9 Shows Searching Facilities

S No.	Searching Facilities	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Boolean operators	0	0%
2.	Wildcard	0	0%
3.	Truncation	0	0%
4.	Simple key word search	51	26%
5.	Other	144	74%
6.	Total	195	100

Table 9 indicates the result of online searching method. In this result shows 144 are using simple key searching, where boolean operator, wildcard and truncation received nothing and other method recieved 51 responses.

The chart 2 shows the results of, is library providing service to you? Where all the responses go to Yes and No with null respond.

Chart 2 Indicate is Service Provided in 1 Library

Table 11 is result of the services reieved from the area of the study, the result indicates on 2% of the responses kn favour of Document Delivery (DD), Selective Dessimination of Information SDI with 21% of the responses, Current Awareness Service CAS with the highest score of 77% in the other hand Translation Service and other services recieved nothing.

Table 11 Indicate the Result of the Service Available in the Library

S No.	Service Provided	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Document Delivery	4	2%
2.	Translation Service	0	0
3.	Current Awareness Service	151	77%
4.	Selective Dissemination of Information	40	21%
5.	Other	0	0
6.	Total	195	100

The chart below depict the respond of do you know method of document arrangement in the library. Yes received 86 responses while No received 109 response.

Chart 3 The Chart above Depict Awareness of Document Arrangement in Library

- In the Table 13 if no do you Receive Formal Orientation, where Yes got no vote and No get all the Responses.

Table 12 Above Indicate Responses of the Respondent on Formal Orientation

S No.	Do you Received Formal Orientation	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Yes	0	0%
2.	No	195	100%
3.	Total	195	100

➤ *And Barriers in Information Seeking*

The challenges faced by the clientele is depicted in the table 13 below the result show lack of professionals have 89 responses, librarians are not friendly received 43 responses, I don't know how to use the library with 59 responses and the environment is not conducive with only 4 respond and others with no respond.

Table 13 Above Depict the Challenges Faced by the Respondent in using the Library

S No.	Problem Face in using Library	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Lack of professional	89	46%
2.	Librarians are not friendly	43	22%
3.	I don't know how to use the library	59	30%
4.	The environment is not conducive	4	2%
5.	Other	0	0%
6.	Total	195	100

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

The research found most of the library users are male and they need information for leisure, and the reasons for information need is for continue education.

The library they mostly visit is public library; it was found article is the most consulted document in the library, in the other hand the frequency of library visitation was found is once in a week and direct searching method is adopted in the library, current awareness services and selective dissemination of information are among the most service provided in the library, it also found the user don't

know document arrangement in the library and no formal orientation is provided by the library.

Among the challenges face by the clientele are lack of professional librarian, librarians are not friendly and most of them they don't know how to use the library.

B. Recommendation

Base on the aforementioned results the following are recommended:

- A formal orientation should be made on regular basis
- The librarians should be sensitized on how to treat their clientele.
- The library environment should be made conducive, in term of lightning, air condition as well as reading space.

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